

THE PROBLEMS OF PROVERBS IN SYNTAX

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ABSTRACT

The study of the syntactic structure of proverbs is one of the tasks before linguistics in determining the stages of the formation of the literary language, its development traditions, and evaluating modern literary language norms. The grammatical features of proverbs refer to the expressive qualities of the word forms used in them, the purposeful selection and substitution of grammatical tools, and the stylistic capabilities of syntactic constructions. To investigate the grammatical features of English proverbs, it is necessary to first consider the syntactic structure of English proverbs

Keywords: The Study Of The Syntactic Structure Of Proverbs, The Grammatical Features Of Proverbs , Proverbs As Independent Elements ,The Positions Of The Proverbs , Partial Changes Of Proverbs.

I. INTRODUCTION

The most valuable ideas about the syntactic structure of English proverbs belong to I.M. Onisanskaya and A.V. Kunin.

According to I.M. Onisanskaya, there is a dependency between meaning and structure in English proverbs. The linguist identifies this dependency in the language of proverbs and the norms of modern language [33, 27].

Onisanskaya describes declarative sentences, which dominate among English proverbs, as expressing truths and facts derived from life experiences [33, 35]. Because of this, the subject is known in such sentences and is usually expressed with the pronouns one, you, or we. For example:

- One beats the bush, and another catches the bird.
- One swallow does not make a summer.
- One nail drives out another.
- We know not what is good until we have lost it.
- We shall see what we shall see.
- You can take a horse to water, but you cannot make him drink.
- You cannot wash charcoal white.

Professor S. Jafarov categorizes proverbs according to their structure as simple and compound [5, 19].

Simple-structured proverbs are mainly one-part or two-part sentences. Proverbs in the form of one-part sentences are often extended one-part sentences with parallel elements expressing opposing meanings, resembling compound sentence types.

When examining the structure of English proverbs, it becomes evident that ideas are expressed concisely and succinctly, giving each sentence component an important role. The omission of any part of the sentence may disrupt the meaning. For instance:

- Don't look a gift horse in the mouth.
- First think, then speak.
- Handsome is that handsome does.
- Great talkers are liars.
- Grasp all, lose all.

If words are removed or abbreviated from the above examples, their meanings would be lost.

Compound English proverbs often contain clauses that characterize a person or object within defining or temporal clauses. For example:

- He who makes no mistakes does nothing.
- He who pleased everybody died before he was born.
- Who has never tasted better knows not what is sweet.

II. AIM

As we know, proverbs are independent sentences; therefore, in many cases, they are not dependent on preceding sentences. Another specific feature of proverbs is their brevity and succinctness. In this regard, compound proverbs often include a single dependent clause.

Another characteristic of proverbs is their stability. However, despite this, proverbs attempt to align with modern language norms. In this context, archaisms in proverbs are mostly seen in the usage of outdated words, with grammatical archaisms being relatively less common. Grammatical archaisms are observed in the following cases [32, 12]:

- a) The use of second-person singular suffixes in the present indefinite tense.
- b) The use of negative verbs without the auxiliary verb "do."
- c) The expression of the subject in the main clause with a personal pronoun.
- d) The use of the conjunction but to connect compound sentences.

From all of this, it can be concluded that the stability of proverbs is characterized by brevity, precise syntax, rhythm, alliteration, etc.

While English proverbs carry various semantic, grammatical, and stylistic functions in speech, they also undergo lexical, morphological, and syntactic changes. In some cases, these changes lead to the formation of new phrases or idiomatic expressions based on the original sentence.

Proverbs are used in speech in two ways:

1. Deductively – Proverbs are incorporated into the context. For example:

"During the first two weeks of September, an increasingly restless expectation spread among the officers. Willie looked to the radio shack, seeking the prayed-for dispatch. Queeg himself showed stirrings of the same eagerness. They say the watched pot never boils."

(H. Wouk)

1. Inductively – Proverbs are addressed in the subsequent sentences. For example:

"Bread at pleasure, drink by measure is also a maxim much to be commended."

(Cheales)

"We have got an old proverb... that 'necessity is the mother of invention.' Take away the necessity, and the invention goes away with it."

(H. Rodger)

Grammatically, proverbs are used in two ways:

1. Syntactically independent – For example:

"She ordered the requisite article and found she had no sunshade to go with the dress. In for a penny, in for a pound, so he bought the sunshade."

(T. Hardy)

"There are two reasons for drinking: one is when you are thirsty, to cure it; the other is when you are not thirsty, to prevent it. Prevention is better than cure."

(T. Peacock)

1. As various sentence elements – For example:

"I wanted him to come back; if we'll do that, we'll let bygones be bygones. After all, we have been married for seventeen years."

(W.S. Maugham)

She was ready to make someone, whether it was him or any other man, the cat's paw if there was a chestnut in the fire.

(A. Kingsley)

The grammatical features of English proverbs are determined by their semantic functions. Proverbs, which fulfill various functions within sentences, are used in two ways: [13.103]

1. In a relatively altered form
2. In a completely altered form

Relatively altered forms of proverbs do not affect their meaning. In such cases, words may be added, their positions may be shifted, or synonyms and antonyms may be included. For example:

- No news (is) good news.
- No sweet without (some) sweat.
- Iron hand (first) in a velvet glove.
- Fortune favors the brave (the bold).
- To draw (pull in one's) horns.

Sometimes, partial changes to proverbs lead to more specific meanings. In such instances, the subject of the sentence may refer to a specific person or object. For example:

- He (Tom) that is ill to himself will be good to nobody.
- Tom (his) money burns a hole in his pocket.

The usage of proverbs in this altered form depends on the author's style.

In the second group of proverbs, all the words remain unchanged, but the relationships between them are altered. In such cases, the structure of the sentence is disrupted, and its general meaning is conveyed through another expression. Over time, these expressions form into idiomatic units within the language, functioning as various sentence elements. [17,127]

A.V. Kunin, who has studied the structure of English proverbs in his textbook "Курс фразеологии английского языка," states that English proverbs are categorized as declarative, interrogative, and imperative sentences in terms of structure. According to Kunin, there are no English proverbs in the form of exclamatory sentences [28, 79].

Thus, agreeing with Kunin's view, it can be noted that syntactically, proverbs are divided into declarative, interrogative, and imperative sentences.

Declarative Proverbs

Before discussing declarative proverbs, let us consider phraseological declarative sentences.

In English, some phraseological units are grammatically structured to express complete thoughts, resembling sentences at first glance.

Researchers studying the phraseology of different languages have referred to such constructions by various names [3, 121]. In modern Russian linguistics, A.V. Yakovlevskaya calls similar phraseological units "fixed expressions" ("устойчивые фразы"). G.A. Selivanov and V.L. Arkhangelsky have also used this term in their works. Among English linguists, N.N. Amosova refers to these as "phraseological units with a predicative structure" ("Фразеологические единицы с предикативной структурой") [22, 135], while A.V. Kunin uses the term "predicative phraseologisms" ("предикативные фразеологизмы") [29, 29]. Additionally, Kunin uses a second term for these constructions, calling them "communicative phraseological units" ("коммуникативные фразеологические единицы").

In German phraseology, I.I. Chernysheva refers to such units as "phraseological expressions" ("фразеологические выражения").

In Azerbaijani linguistics, S. Murtuzayev refers to such constructions as "phraseological sentences," while Ə. Demirchizade calls them "idiomatic sentences" [6, 172].

Linguistic evidence shows that some constructions, expressed with declarative intonation, can also function as grammatical interrogative sentences by adding question words.

Thus, based on H. Bayramov's views, we can identify two types of phraseological sentences [3, 122].

1. Phraseological Declarative Sentences
2. Phraseological Interrogative Sentences

The specific characteristic of phraseological declarative sentences is that, although the ideas expressed in them may pertain to a particular person, the word denoting that person does not function as an independent subject

within the phraseological sentence. It is precisely this feature that distinguishes such constructions from grammatical (syntactic) sentences.

In our language, the noun component of phraseological units formed based on the noun + verb model is expressed through nouns denoting body parts like leg, head, mouth, hand, heart, eye or through abstract/concrete nouns such as think, supposition, blood, house. Additionally, in some phraseological declarative sentences, the predicate is expressed through nouns. Thus, these types of phraseological declarative sentences, at first glance, resemble grammatical (syntactic) sentences with verbal or nominal predicates.

It should be noted that some linguists studying impersonal sentences in English include a subset of phraseological sentences in this category, thereby equating the two.

In some phraseological declarative sentences, the predicate is expressed with verbs, while in others, it is expressed with nouns. Taking this into account, such constructions should be divided into two groups:

1. Phraseological declarative sentences with verbal predicates
2. Phraseological declarative sentences with nominal predicates [3, 123].

Phraseological Declarative Sentences with Verbal Predicates

Some phraseological constructions of this type are used to express certain states or actions, while others are used to describe the person being referred to. From this perspective, phraseological declarative sentences with verbal predicates can be classified into two groups:

1. Those expressing states or actions
2. Those with descriptive content.

Sentences Expressing States or Actions

There are various structural types of phraseological declarative sentences in this group in our language. Here, we will examine the structural types that include the most phraseological sentences:

- a) Possessive or attributive phrases (or their second components) + verb constructions

Phraseological sentences with such a structure are more common than other structural types in English [3, 123].

It should be noted that there are certain similarities and differences between phraseological declarative sentences of this type and verbal phraseological combinations. The similarity lies in the fact that some of these constructions are formed by converting the verb component from active to passive voice or from causative to active voice, maintaining the same lexical composition.

The difference is that some of these phraseological declarative sentences correspond to verbal phraseological combinations in the language. Additionally, in some cases, by making specific modifications to the verb components of such constructions, they can also be used as verbal phraseological combinations in English.

- b) Similar to type "to" but requiring an object in the dative case

Some phraseological declarative sentences possess the characteristics of type "to" but also require an object in the dative case, depending on the established content of the language. This object may answer the questions "to whom?" or "to what?", or both, and may consist of a phrase or its second component [3, 125].

- c) Similar to type "to" but requiring an object in the accusative case

Some phraseological declarative sentences in English have characteristics similar to type "to," but depending on their meaning, they require an object in the accusative case. These objects answer questions such as "whom?" or "what?".

- d) Similar to type "from" but requiring an object in the ablative case

This subgroup of phraseological sentences demands an object in the ablative case based on their fixed meanings in the language. These objects answer questions such as "from whom?" or "from what?" [3, 126].

- e) Similar to type "to," but requiring objects in the locative or directive cases

Some phraseological declarative sentences in English demand objects in the locative case, often answering the question "where?".

- f) Containing an additional permanent nominal component

In such phraseological units, a third permanent component appears as a nominal element in the nominative case.

g) Similar to type "to," but with a third component governed by the verb in the dative case

In some three-component verbal phraseological units, the third component governed by the verb acts as a fixed element in the dative case.

h) Similar to type "to," but with a second component governed by the verb in the locative case

In certain phraseological sentences in English, the second component governed by the verb differs from type "to" by being expressed in the locative case rather than without a suffix [3, 128].

i) Similar to type "to," but with an adverb as the second component governed by the verb

In such three-component phraseological units, the second component governed by the verb is an adverb. Despite differences in the specific features of these phraseological sentences, the common aspect is that, although the idea expressed pertains to a particular person, that person does not serve as an independent subject of the phraseological sentence. Instead, the word associated with the person acts as the head component of the phraseological unit, playing a leading role.

As such, it is not the person themselves but the word associated with them (the head component of the phraseological unit) that takes precedence, while the person expressed as the first component serves to specify and clarify meaning.

j) Subjects with a Variable Nature, Permanent Components in the Structure of Possessive Phrases (or Type III Attributive Phrases) + Verb

To construct phraseological sentences of such units, depending on the content of the idea, a conditional subject is added to the fixed phrase. This subject can consist of a single word or various types of word combinations.

It should be noted that among these, those associated with the thought process are expanded conditionally and can appear in structures resembling subordinate clauses. In such cases, the phraseological construction resembles a complex sentence with a subordinate clause. However, these are fundamentally different categories. [14,114]

III. METHODOLOGY

As seen, components functioning as subordinate clauses are, in essence, expanded forms of the conditional subject of verb phraseological units with the above-mentioned features. Therefore, we can express such sentences as simple sentences. In works discussing English syntax, these types of sentences—i.e., those that resemble complex sentences with a subject clause or similar constructions at first glance—are categorized as complex sentences with subject clauses.

However, in our opinion, equating phraseological constructions with purely grammatical (syntactic) constructions is inappropriate; because, in complex sentences with subject clauses, the words within are used in their nominative meanings, making the syntactic relationships among them purely grammatical. In contrast, in the examples provided above, the words interact on a phraseological level, not based on their nominative meanings. Hence, the syntactic relationships in such cases do not merely serve grammatical expression but also contribute to the phraseological meaning. [21,101]

Considering this, we believe that including such constructions under the category of complex sentences in works on English syntax is incorrect, as it equates grammatical categories with phraseological ones [3, 131].

Those with a Descriptive Nature

In English, a small portion of verb-based phraseological declarative sentences express the figurative characteristics of the person, place, etc., being discussed. These sentences are structurally verb-based phraseological sentences and are identical to the phraseological sentences discussed in the previous group in this regard. However, they do not convey the performance of a specific action but instead provide a figurative depiction of a state or condition. Due to this distinguishing feature, it is appropriate to call these "descriptive verb-predicate phraseological declarative sentences." [24,84]

In such constructions, the description can have either a positive or negative connotation.

Descriptive phraseological units can be applied not only to humans [14, 37] but also to objects and their characteristics. In this regard, phraseological units are quite diverse.

Noun-Predicate Phraseological Declarative Sentences

Noun-predicate declarative sentences are divided into two groups:

1. Those indicating the performance of a specific action
2. Those with descriptive characteristics [25, 134].

1) Those Indicating the Performance of a Specific Action

In English, there are several noun-predicate declarative sentences, most of which describe a state or condition. These sentences are equivalent to grammatical sentences with static verbs as predicates. Such phraseological noun-predicate sentences are limited in our language. Most of them are formed with the names of certain body parts, while a few are formed with other common nouns.

2) Those with Descriptive Characteristics

As in verb-predicate phraseological declarative sentences, some noun-predicate phraseological declarative sentences also carry descriptive content. These can also be used in either a positive or negative context.

Noun-predicate phraseological declarative sentences express diverse descriptive characteristics based on their content.

Non-Predicative Constructions Formed from Verb Phraseological Declarative Sentences

In speech, constructions in the form of verb phraseological declarative sentences can also be used in non-predicative forms. These forms are created through suffixes for participles, gerunds, or Type III attributive word combinations, similar to grammatical word combinations.

However, it should be noted that the words forming such fixed constructions with phraseological and predicative structures do not all have the same nature. In this regard, the words within phraseological sentences should be divided into two groups.

The words in the first group act as the main components shaping the meaning of the fixed combination. The components in the second group, however, convey concepts such as a person, object, etc., depending on the general content of the phraseological sentence, and are therefore variable based on the meaning of the phraseological unit [3, 135].

Such constructions derived from verb phraseological sentences are also used with participle, gerund, and other suffixes. In a non-predicative context, they resemble syntactic categories like participial phrases, gerundive phrases, or attributive combinations in English.

Therefore, authors discussing English syntax have thus far equated such constructions with these syntactic categories based on external similarity. However, these are not formed from free word combinations but are non-predicative constructions derived from fixed combinations creating verb phraseological sentences.

Considering this, it is necessary to name such fixed combinations appropriately to distinguish them from free word combinations, attributive word combinations, and structures formed from these [3, 136–137].

We suggest naming those formed with participle suffixes as "participial structures derived from phraseological sentences," those formed with gerund suffixes as "gerundive structures derived from phraseological sentences," and those resembling attributive word combinations as "Type III attributive word combinations derived from phraseological sentences."

Some of these forms are widely used in our language.

Thus, it becomes clear that the characteristics of verb phraseological sentences discussed here are used in English as various types of word combinations based on grammatical rules in non-predicative forms. However, such combinations fundamentally differ from purely syntactic word combinations in English. Therefore, they should not be equated with free word combinations.

The form of proverbs in English is divided into simple affirmative sentences and simple negative sentences [28, 80].

1. In simple affirmative sentences, something is affirmed or denied. In these sentences, the subject is mostly expressed by a noun. For example:

1. An apple a day keeps the doctor away.
2. Dump dogs are dangerous.
3. Happiness takes no account of time.

In proverbs with a complex sentence structure, a personal pronoun replaces the subject. For example:

- Birds of a feather flock together.
- Su axar çuxuru tapar (The water flows and finds its own path).
- Fish begins to stink at the head.
- One swallow doesn't make a spring.
- A single swallow does not bring summer = one bird doesn't make spring.

Simple structured proverbs, besides being used independently, can also be used within complex sentence structures. For example:

- You must not forget that there is still the possibility that the girl Cataline Peres was deceived. The proof of the pudding is in the eating. (W.S. Maugham)
- They will tell you that the proof of the pudding is in the eating, and they are right. (K. Share)

1. In simple negative sentences, all methods of expressing negation are used. In such proverbs, negation is mainly expressed through the first-person form of the auxiliary verb “do” + not or the “can + not” particles (expressed via forms like doesn't, didn't, aren't) [30, 82]. For example:

- Don't look a gift horse in the mouth.
- Don't put all your eggs in one basket.
- Love cannot be forced.

The subject in simple negative sentences is expressed by pronouns and nouns. For example:

- You cannot flay the same ox twice.
- You cannot peel the same ox twice = you can't get two hides from one sheep.
- Crows do not pick out crows' eyes.
- A dog doesn't step on another dog's feet.

Among simple sentence structured proverbs, there are types like indefinite-person, general-person, singular, incomplete, elliptical, and dual-membered sentences.

There are also cases where the subject is not grammatically expressed in proverbs. This is primarily found in incomplete and elliptical constructions. Elliptical and incomplete sentences will be discussed shortly [4, 47].

In proverbs, the word order—specifically the order of the subject and predicate—may be disrupted. This signifies a violation of the grammatical rules of sentence formation. This rule pertains to the style of the language, but such a violation in proverbs does not make the speech heavy. It does not create intonational inconsistencies because proverbs, as the results of historical processes, have been in use for a long period and are universally accepted in their specific forms. For example:

- A poor man's horse does not go far.
- A madman is not given a stick.

Linguists argue that the key element in such forms is intonation fluidity. Unlike scientific style, which is rigid, literary style often uses such word order deviations as a tool to more effectively convey a thought. Thus, word order in this case serves to create a specific style. However, not all disruptions generate emotional undertones. When serving a specific purpose, style nuances emerge [4, 55].

Incomplete sentences have not yet been precisely defined in linguistics. Some linguists consider them to be sentences in which one or both components are omitted, while others expand the definition to include cases where secondary components are missing.

Regarding incomplete sentence structures in proverbs, it should be noted that this group of proverbs is more common in dialogic speech, particularly in response parts. As mentioned, incomplete sentences omit one or another part of the sentence. This feature is also found in proverbs with incomplete sentence structures.

a) Proverbs with missing subjects in incomplete sentence structures. For example:

- Whose house is this? – The one sitting.

- Whose words are these? – The one speaking.
- Bald man, did you wash your head? – I washed and combed.

In this example, "I washed" is the response. "I combed" serves as an expression that strengthens the meaning and adds expressiveness, making it an intensified lexical unit added stylistically to the sentence type.

b) Proverbs with omitted predicates in incomplete sentence structures. These are more common in dialogic speech. For example:

- Burnt cattle, where are you going? – To burn.
- What does a blind person want? – Two eyes, one crooked, one straight.

In the provided examples, the use of question sentences serves more of a stylistic function than to simply seek an answer. Rhetorical questions, in particular, draw attention to the thought and emphasize a distinction from others. The question loses its primary function, and the answer in the response reaches the peak of meaning.

c) Proverbs with missing complements in incomplete sentence structures. These, like other incomplete sentence proverbs, are frequently used in dialogic speech. These sentences lack a complete complement, and the second-degree component—the complement—is omitted, meaning it is missing or incomplete [4, 58].

For example:

- Whose house is this? – The one sitting.
- Whose words are these? – The one speaking.

It is clear that in the response part, the absence of the complement means the thought is not fully expressed. The omission of the complement corresponds to a dialogic form expressed with impactful verbs, which semantically and grammatically creates a connection by requiring a complement.

Elliptical sentence constructions in proverbs follow the principle of economy, and ellipsis often occurs in spoken language. Depending on the context, a part of the sentence may be omitted, but the full thought is still communicated. In proverbs, ellipsis is more often seen, and the omission of the component makes the thought more emotional and impactful [6, 47]. Elliptical sentence constructions in proverbs show ellipsis at two levels:

1. At the affix level.
2. At the word and phrase level.

Ellipsis at the affix level is frequently encountered in literature and oral creativity. Regardless of the sentence structure, it is quickly restored. In proverbs, the most commonly ellipsized affix is the verb "is." For example:

- Blood is thicker than water (is).
- A woman is a housewife, a man is a worker (is).
- The father chops, the son eats (is).
- The ram's horn is not a load (is).

In the example, even though the affix is omitted, it can be easily restored. This affix's other feature is that it does not take stress. The omission of this affix in proverbs creates strong expressiveness and emotional impact, which is linked to the emphasis in the final word.

At the word level, ellipsis means omitting a part of a phrase or sentence. For example:

- Nothing (is) so bad but it might have been worse.

One thinks, the other gives thanks (thinks).

The mad likes the mad, the priest likes halva (likes).

The expressions of proverbs with elliptical structures (reduced news) express general authority, confidence, advice, and especially stylistic features [6, 49].

In proverbs, ellipsis in the form of the reduction of the first component of word combinations is more commonly encountered (strong emotionality, conciseness, expressiveness serve creativity).

For example:

His father eats sour apples, his son's teeth are sharp.

My grandfather called me blind, and said to hit whoever comes and goes.

As seen, in such sentences, the omission of a part of a sentence component serves to create strong emotionality, conciseness, and expressiveness. In proverbs, they often increase the difficulty of the command, add emotionality to the sentence structure, and thus contribute to the enhancement of literary quality and fluency. These are not consciously thought-out forms, but have been shaped and polished over time, and are related to the genre characteristics of the literary style of the language. These characteristics are the reason why elliptical forms of proverbs are effective.

Complex Sentence Structure Proverbs

A.V. Kunin, in addition to simple declarative sentence structure proverbs, also presents proverbs with complex sentence structures [28, 145]. Complex sentence structure proverbs are divided into two types: subordinate and coordinate complex sentences.

1. Coordinate Complex Proverbs

A coordinate complex sentence is not a random combination of several different sentences, but rather a grammatically-semantic combination that is united by specific grammatical means such as conjunctions, meaning relationships, and is accompanied by unifying intonation. For example:

The scalded cat (dog) fears cold water.

A cock is valiant on his own dunghill.

Dump dogs are dangerous.

Fine feathers make fine birds.

As we know, in a coordinate complex sentence, the components are independent clauses, while in a subordinate complex sentence, one part is the main clause and the other is a subordinate clause (sentence). Proverbs with subordinate complex sentence structures are based on this principle. Although the components of a complex sentence have an independent sentence form, they do not have their own separate intonation. They are included in the final intonation of the combined sentence. The issue of "independence" is taken in comparison to the subordinate clause. It appears to be grammatically independent compared to the subordinate clause.

Most coordinate complex proverbs are constructed without conjunctions, while the majority of subordinate complex proverbs use conjunctions [29, 148]. For example:

He must have iron nails that scratches a bear.

He that will steal an egg will steal an ox.

He who is born a fool is never cured.

If life hands you lemons, make lemonade.

Fortune is easily found, but hard to be kept.

As is known, the syntax section of English linguistics, especially the stylistic features of complex sentences, is one of the least studied areas.

Proverbs in complex sentence form, and sayings, do not have any distinctive formal features, so we can consider these features as specific genre characteristics.

As we know, the components of coordinate complex sentences are not subordinated to one another, and they are equal clauses. However, there are semantic relationships between them. In the structure of these types of sentences, the lexical-semantic features of the components, as well as their intonation-stylistic aspects, reveal many notable characteristics.

Research shows that coordinate complex sentences are closer to spoken language. When we look at proverbs of this type without conjunctions, we see that in these sentences, intonation and emphasis take a leading role, and thus the proverbs are closer to the norms of common spoken language. The construction features that can replace a conjunction are not insignificant. This also includes the morphological formation of coordinate complex sentences.

Although proverbs with coordinate complex sentence structures are rare in English, the relationships between their components stand out [27, 150].

a) Formed between concession (contradiction) relations. For example:

It never rains, but it pours.

Agues come on horseback but go away on foot.

When fever comes, it comes on horseback, but when it leaves, it goes on foot = Troubles come like a whirlwind, but go away with a small sound.

b) Formed Based on Restriction Relation, for example:

- The pitcher goes often to the well, but it's broken at last.
- Laws catch flies but let hornets go free.
- The law is like a spider's web: it catches the flies, but lets the hornets go free = Sharia is for the common people.

c) Formed Based on Unification, Succession Relation, for example:

- As you sow, you shall mow.
- March comes in like a lion and goes out like a lamb.
- March comes in like a lion and goes out like a lamb.
- As you brew, you must drink.
- As you make your bed, you must lie on it.

d) Formed Based on Relativity Relation, for example:

- There is one good wife in the country every man thinks he has her.

In Azerbaijani, the following relations exist between the components of a non-dependent compound sentence [17, 99]

a) Comparison-related non-dependent compound sentences

As we know, if the idea expressed in one part of a non-dependent compound sentence is opposite to the idea expressed in the other part, the relation between them is comparative. In such sentences, the contradiction can be created either through the lexical-semantic meanings of the sentence's predicate or through comparison with the subject and adverbial of the first part, and the subject and adverbial of the second part. For example:

- Beautiful appears, ugly is covered.
- You may wear my slippers, but you cannot walk as I do.

In non-dependent compound sentences with this type, the omission of the predicate in the second component reflects stylistic characteristics. For example:

- The snake waits for the man's heel, and the man waits for the snake's head.
- Look at the hat on the head, at the clothes on the body.

As can be seen, the omission of the predicate here still keeps the meaning clear, and it helps form a harmony in the style of expression.

b) Succession-related non-dependent compound sentences

In non-dependent compound sentences with succession, the time order of actions in the components is sequential. Changing their order is not difficult. However, while the time of the action in the components may not be highly noticeable, a certain difference will be evident. For example:

- The lord fought with the lord, and the servant lost his life.
- The madman threw a stone into the well, but a thousand wise men could not pull it out.

c) Cause-and-effect related non-dependent compound sentences

This relationship often has more stylistic features in non-dependent compound sentences. In these sentences, the expressive characteristic is created by linking the cause to the effect, or vice versa, at a specific moment. For example:

- I gave it out of madness, you return it with wisdom.
- The one who walks will get swollen feet, but the one who sits will have a swollen head.

In the above examples, the expression is created by intonation. The specific tone and emphasis accompanying the sentences is an important characteristic. The tenses of the verbs may also appear in a range of rich stylistic

features, and the use of antonyms or negation intensifies the stylistic effect and gives the expression more depth.

For example:

- Wisdom exists, but money does not; money exists, but wisdom does not.
- One fell, the other stood up.

These non-dependent compound sentences with cause-and-effect relations stand out for their clarity and smoothness, and the content and meaning are more profound.

a) Time-related non-dependent compound sentences

Another relation between the components of non-dependent compound sentences is the time relation. This can either be simultaneous or sequential. In proverbs, simultaneity is generally conveyed through intonation, indicating that the actions or states are carried out at the same time or continuously. Such examples may have verbal or nominal predicates in their components. For example:

- Touch the rich, pass the poor.
- If you starve, you'll become a thief; if you talk too much, you'll become shameless.
- I saw the shepherd without a dog, and I saw the time without a clock.

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the syntactic and grammatical analysis of English proverbs reveals their remarkable structural and stylistic complexity, despite their seemingly simple and concise form. This study has demonstrated that proverbs are not only fixed expressions rooted in cultural and historical experiences but also dynamic linguistic units that function effectively across various syntactic roles and discourse contexts. The research affirms that English proverbs typically follow the structure of declarative, interrogative, or imperative sentences, with a dominance of declarative forms. Their syntactic forms range from simple and compound to complex structures, including elliptical and incomplete sentence types. This diversity reflects their adaptability and stylistic richness in spoken and written communication. Proverbs frequently employ rhetorical strategies such as ellipsis, inversion, and coordination to enhance emotional impact, rhythm, and fluency, allowing them to function both as standalone expressions and as integrated components of broader textual discourse. Furthermore, the study highlights that while proverbs exhibit a high degree of stability, they are still subject to morphological, lexical, and syntactic variation depending on the speaker's intent, stylistic choices, or contextual demands. The nuanced use of proverbs—whether inductively or deductively, syntactically independent or embedded—demonstrates their functional flexibility in language. Ultimately, English proverbs serve as a valuable resource for understanding the evolution and norms of modern literary language. Their grammatical features, shaped by tradition yet responsive to linguistic change, reflect both the constancy and adaptability of linguistic expression. As this study shows, the syntactic structure of proverbs is not merely a matter of form but a reflection of deep-seated linguistic, cultural, and cognitive patterns that continue to shape English usage today..

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